

Correctional Inmates' Vocational Training and Crime Control Measures in Calabar and Obubra Custodial Centers, Nigeria

¹Ikahokhuele, Lucky, ²Oboh, Isaac Omojiade (Ph.D.), & ³Ogbu Uduma Michael

^{1&2} Department of Sociology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria. ikahos@aauekpoma.edu.ng; ¹ikaholuck123@yahoo.com. ²Obohisaac04@gmail.com

³Department of Sociology and Anthropology, Faculty of Social Science, University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State. ogbumichael128@gmail.com

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Abstract

Inmate vocational training involves implementing educational and skills-based programs aimed at transforming inmates' values, preparing them for employment, and facilitating their effective reintegration into society upon release. This study examined the relationship between correctional inmates' vocational training and crime control in Calabar and Obubra custodial centers in Cross River State, Nigeria. The structural functionalist perspective of Radcliff Brown was used to explain the subject matter. A survey design was employed, utilizing a structured questionnaire and a multi-stage sampling approach that combined purposive and cluster sampling techniques, involving 200 respondents. Demographic data were analyzed using frequency methods, while the hypothesis was tested with Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient, skewness, and kurtosis methods. Findings indicate that vocational training for inmates can significantly influence crime control in these custodial centers. The study concludes that health and vocational training are essential needs for inmates, and the quality of their correction can be judged by their ability to control criminal behavior in society. It is recommended that government at all levels recognize the importance of vocational training for inmates as an effective mechanism for crime control, which can contribute to restructuring the Nigerian Correctional Service (NCS) and ultimately aid in reducing crime.

Keywords: *Correction, Inmates, Vocation Training, Crime, Crime Control, Custodial Center.*

Introduction

This study views vocational training of inmates as a means of reformation and rehabilitation to help them lead a meaningful life when they are discharged. It also means changing inmates' values and training them in educational or skill-based training to be employable on discharge. The correctional environment, with its different culture and ways of life, shows a complete design with the desire to change the behaviors of inmates for good or bad, depending on the social conditions and experience of such inmates. This is so because the social network that inmates experience and the type of vocational training they receive combine to determine their eventual realities both within and outside the correctional facilities upon their release. The pattern of doing things in the corrections in terms of vocational training of inmates shows the means and ways for the adjustment processes of inmates. Its culture is dynamic, which comprises all sorts of value reorientation and internalization (Obioha, 2011).

The fundamental aims of establishing a correctional institution all over the world, including Nigeria, are to provide rehabilitation, vocational training for inmates, and correctional facilities for those who have violated the laws of society. However, these objectives have not been effectively met due to loopholes in the correctional system (NCS Act, 2019; Custodial Standing Order, 2020). According to Obioha (2011), the correctional institutions have become

a training avenue for criminals instead of vocational training centers for inmates and rehabilitation homes in Nigeria. A critical look at the individuals who go in and out of the Nigerian Correctional Services (NCS) reveals several issues within the system. This brings the argument that the NCS has not lived up to its expectations in terms of vocational training of inmates and positively impacting the lives of the inmates, thereby helping to control crime.

However, in trying to carry out this vocational training of inmates, Calabar and Obubra custodial centers are faced with problems ranging from dilapidated accommodation, inadequate medical facilities, inadequate vocational training and learning facilities for inmates, inadequate finance, inadequate personnel, and lack of motivation. Most buildings were built in 1958 and 1927, respectively, which cannot fit the present day's inmates' vocational training, which has greatly affected the reformation and rehabilitation of the corrections and undermined the corrections' effectiveness in crime control (Davidson, Olaolu, & Ezeobi, 2012). The aforementioned problems led to jailbreak by inmates in Calabar, which led to the death of eight inmates and several others wounded, including staff (Kalu, 2015).

Notwithstanding, the correctional institutions are expected to beef up skills acquisition, its infrastructure for adult and remedial education, and psychotherapy sessions to transform those sentenced to jail terms. Skills and vocational training in NCS are carpentry, shoemaking, electricity, and metal work, printing, tailoring, etc., if acquired by inmates, would assist them in earning a living on discharge without relapsing to crime (Kalu, 2015). Against this background, this paper seeks to know how correctional inmate vocational training, which includes aftercare service, earning scheme, and one-third remission, can control crime and criminalities in NCS and Nigerian society at large. Generally, the study examined correctional inmates' vocational training and crime control measures in Calabar and Obubra custodial centers of Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined vocational training/aftercare service, earning scheme, and one-third remission, and crime control in the study areas.

Research Hypothesis

There is no significant association between vocational training of correctional inmates and crime control in Calabar and Obubra custodial centres.

Literature Review

Vocational Training of Inmates

Vocational training refers to training in different skills acquisition and teaching of specific trades, vocations, and occupations which the recipient wishes to pursue to enable such an individual to be employable upon discharge (UNESCO, 2023). It also means an instructional programme that is centered on the acquired skills for a specific trade or job. In vocational training, education is the cornerstone for preparing students or participants for a particular career, including traditional prospects and unrelated academic subjects. Some of the skills involved in vocational

training include automotive repair, plumbing, graphic art, fashion design, agriculture, home economics, Information Communication Technology (ICT), culinary art, and welding, among others (Career Guide, 2023).

The primary objective of vocational training is to allow participants to have practical experience in their chosen career aspect when they graduate. Participants who have completed their rigorous programmes are equipped with training skills and certificates to start their chosen career upon graduation. Despite the participants' confidence in their various abilities, their employers themselves are also confident in their choices and believe they would excel in their positions respectively (Jens-Henning, 2023). The vitality of vocational training creates usefulness for those who possess the skills required, as a creative person. We have seen some mind-blowing designs of cakes, fashion, and furniture, among others. Even the recent applications of Ankara and jeans materials in making bags, shoes, and clothing are examples of creative minds. Vocational training, therefore, enables a person's skills and ideals to invent new things for human consumption (Akinade, 2020).

Furthermore, vocational training serves as a medium of income generation. Most people may acquire vocational training for diverse reasons, but whatever reason given, it is to generate income. It also boosts someone's networks. That is, acquiring a vocational training skill can pave the way for strong network connections to customers. The ability to present specific vocational training skills could be an asset to participants or students seeking admission within and outside Nigeria. Vocational training also led one to become an agent of change, providing an avenue to develop life skills of an individual, among others (Akinade, 2020).

However, inmates in correctional institutions are effectively trained in the industrial session and are empowered with modern tools for effective rehabilitation to society upon discharge, and there is a monitoring team that takes care of this; the "welfare service" and the "After-care service officers" of the NCS ensure continuity of trades learnt in the correctional centre. This helps to prevent them from going back to crime and criminality (Ogundipe, 2008, 2010, & 2012). Nkwocha (2018) opined that, on admission, every inmate is allowed a choice of vocation he/she want to learn while in the correctional institution, though under the guidance of the options available. This is made known to the inmates by the admission board constituted by the person in charge of correction, which must be guided by the Standing Order (S.O.) of the NCS. He (Nkwocha) further opines that this brought into existence the process of reformation and rehabilitation as the inmate is introduced to the skills they want to acquire for their eventual resettlement on discharge. While they are learning the skills or trades, they are also undergoing character development. The person in charge, who is also a correctional officer, is on duty for the reformatory work on the inmate.

Cox and Wade (1989) in Nkwocha (2018) argued that the fundamental belief of rehabilitation as a correctional aim is that behaviour can be changed if we know the prior history of the individual involved (and about the causes of the undesirable criminal behaviour). e.g., A person identified as committing utilitarian burglary as a result of being a school dropout and having no vocational skills might be placed in an educational and vocational training

programme that would provide the skills necessary to ensure and retain reasonable employment, thereby abandoning the need to commit burglaries. The department responsible for vocational training of inmates in NCS is the “Directorate of Inmates Training and Productivity”. The department is responsible for earning a practical living in the larger society. Reasonable programmes in the vocational training of inmates began from the industry, which includes tailoring, carpentry, welding, shoe making, iron bending, barbing, among others. Those from the rural environment are deployed into correctional farm centers where they are trained in modern agriculture which includes modern crops production techniques, animal husbandry, farm machinery (use of tractor in plugging, harrowing, planting, fertilizer application and integrated weed control toward effective food production for the timing population (Custodial Standing Order, 2020; Imobhio, 2021; 2022 & 2023).

Kalu (2015) opined that this treatment and vocational training of inmates are stipulated within broad categories namely: (a) Provision of work for inmates that help them to earn their living on discharge; (b) Educational attention; the exercise to personal influence on the individual by members of the correctional staff; and, the provision of possible opportunities for the development of personal responsibility, including, for suitable inmates, training in open conditions. Categories ‘a and ‘b’ of the treatment and vocational training are vital to the issue under investigation - ‘vocational training of inmates and crime control.’ What ‘a’ above implies is that those who commit crimes are those who have no work or skills for work. Through correctional farms and industries, those inmates are equipped with skills to take care of themselves on discharge. The implication of ‘b’ above is based on the knowledge that those who commit a crime need to acquire education both for skills development and training of the mind for self-development (Custodial Standing Order, 2020).

Armed with these, the correctional institutions are expected to beef up skills acquisition, their fundamental need for adult education, and psychological training sessions to rehabilitate those sentenced to jail terms. Skills and vocations training in NCS are carpentry, shoemaking, electricity, metal work, printing, and tailoring, among others. If acquired by inmates, assist them in earning a living on discharge without relapsing to crime (Kalu, 2015).

Vocational Training and Crime Control

Crime control refers to efforts designed to keep crime in effective check, to keep it from spreading widely, to restrict and prevent crime infection and contamination, to prevent crime from breaking, and to protect society against the activities of offenders. Crime is controlled using effective and efficient investigative and detective abilities and actions, which prompt apprehension and prosecution of convicts, effective and prompt action in dealing with criminal activities in order to produce repressive or deterrent effects on habitual and would-be offenders (Igbo, 2009). However, there are several rehabilitative and reformatory programmes and policies of discharging inmates to effect crime control measures in and outside their place of confinement, some are as follows: ‘Aftercare Service’ as one of the rehabilitative programmes came into existence in the 1950s, though its operation was not clearly defined. Aftercare service in the NCS was renamed in 2003; scheduled officers were appointed, trained, and an

informative handbill was prepared to educate those in contact with Aftercare officers. Aftercare in Nigerian setting is a post-release programme and its major component is the provision of tools to discharging inmates. Funding over the years was poor, thus hindering the effectiveness of services provided (Tunde, 2016).

It is a package of interventions which includes provision of tools, enlistment in post-custodial apprenticeship vocational training, development of life-skills, building relationships with families, provision of housing, and business premises, among others (Tunde, 2016). Tunde further defined aftercare service as the conscious governmental and civil society initiative to enable inmates to surmount all forms of discrimination against their social rehabilitation in the community. It is a social rehabilitation programme for inmates upon their discharge; it is where inmates are taught how to succeed outside the correctional environment and are given the tools to succeed. This has also helped to control crime and criminality among ex-convicts.

The major beneficiary of this service is society. Where inmates are not vocationally trained and given the benefit of After-care service, the probability of re-offence is increased, and society is exposed to more injury. The inmates also stand to benefit since they are equipped via the After-care services to lead a productive, law-abiding life. Inmates who followed their sentencing plan and programmes through and have responded positively to behaviour modification are also to benefit from the After-care service. The period is between six months to one year (Nkwocha, 2018). However, the NCS currently has 7 Aftercare centers for this purpose in Benin, Umuahia, Lagos, Ibadan, Potiskum, Sokoto and Keffi and this represents each of the geo-political zones (Ogundipe, 2010 & 2012).

Another programme designed to rehabilitate discharging inmates in NCS for crime control measures is the “Earning scheme”. This is a scheme that provides monthly payments to convicted inmates while in custody. The government introduced it to pacify the minds of the inmates. It also shows that the government remembers inmates and at least could provide aid to them. The scheme provides payment of different amounts to different categories of convicts or inmates. The scheme is handled by the officer in charge of welfare in the correctional center, and supervised by the officer in charge of the correctional center (Nkwocha, 2018).

Inmates entitled to the scheme are always pre-informed. They are not given their money to keep; instead, the welfare officers open a book where any payment made is recorded against the inmates’ names. The only two avenues for the use of the money by the inmates are: (a) to be used to purchase things for themselves, but not exceeding half of the money; (b) to start life again after being discharged. The scheme enhances rehabilitation, reformation, and correction of inmates and was introduced by R. H. Dolan in 1947 (Nkwocha, 2008). This also helped to deter them from crime in and outside custody.

Next is “one-third remission as a means of crime control measure”. This is a basic tool for effective rehabilitation and reformation. Remission of one-third of the sentence is awarded only to an inmate serving a sentence or cumulative sentence that exceeds one month. However, no convict serving such sentence(s) shall serve for a period

less than 30 days (Loveday, 2020). The Custodial Standard Order (2020) empowers the corrections authority to divide an inmate's sentence into three and remove one of the three divisions for a well-behaved inmate. For instance, if an inmate is sentenced to 3 three months confinement, with one-third remission, the prisoner serves only 2 two months. For this reason, inmates work very hard to earn one-third of their sentences. This ambition for the remission, which encourages good behaviour, is a good environment for rehabilitation and reformation. The correction officers then capitalize on this submission to rules and regulations and instill the spirit of positive change in them, even after being discharged (Frank & John, 2017). This is also an aspect of crime control measures in NCS. There are other packages aimed at implementing effective reformation, rehabilitation, and crime control measures to social deviance in the correctional institutions. These include Amnesty, Chaplaincy fund, therapy and counseling, educational programs, free venture programmes, among others.

Theoretical Framework

This paper adopts the Structural-functionalist theory of Radcliff Brown. Alfred Radcliffe-Brown (1881-1955) was an English social anthropologist who developed the theory of Structural Functionalism. Radcliffe-Brown focused attention on social structure. He posited that a society is a system of relationships maintaining itself through cybernetic feedback. At the same time, social institutions are ordered sets of relationships aimed at maintaining the smooth running of the system. Radcliffe-Brown, a follower of Auguste Comte, believed that society constituted a separate "level" of reality different from those of biological forms and inorganic matter. Moreover, he argued that explanations of social issues had to be constructed within the social level. He believed that persons were replaceable, transient occupants of social roles (Goldschmidt, 1996).

Radcliffe-Brown carried out his research on what accounts for different structures, which in the reverse case leads to functions that ultimately deal with how structures maintain society. For him, function is the prerequisite of structure in social existence. He opined that the social system (society) has a functionality of unity: All parts function together for the maintenance of the society (Turner, 2002). Functional analysis paved the way for a novel alternative: structures that are analysed, such as kinship or ritual activities, in terms of their functionalities for maintaining the society.

However, the core idea of this theory is that social structure is an abstraction based on social relationships, allowing society to be divided into three main levels: individuals, institutions, and sub-systems. Similar to society, when applying this assumption to the vocational training of inmates in correctional institutions, the correctional system itself is viewed as a functional, structural whole with different parts, such as the vocational training of inmates. This suggests that elements of the correctional institutions' way of life, including norms, values, and folkways, are integral to the vocational training of inmates—helping to influence crime, social control, and other behavioral patterns both within and outside correctional institutions (Adetula, Adutula & Fatusin, 2010).

This theory has been criticized in that society’s survival depended on institutional practices. This notion, cum the belief that the different segment system selected the viable talented persons to meet society’s needs, was viewed by some as an ideal meant to legitimize the status quo and thereby hinder vocational training and social reform of the inmates. It was also criticized for not recognizing the efficiency of individuals within the society.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is the survey approach as proposed by Nwagbara (2007). The population of the study includes male and female correctional staff aged 18-65 years, totaling 246 staff from both Calabar and Obubra correctional centers (Oti, 2018). The population comprises 134 male staff and 42 female staff from Calabar correctional facility, as well as 57 male and 13 female officials from Obubra correctional facility. The sampling technique used for the study was purposive. Consequently, 200 respondents were selected and given questionnaires from Calabar and Obubra correctional centers. Of these, 150 were from Calabar, and 50 from Obubra. The selected respondents had been in service for at least three years, ensuring they have adequate firsthand knowledge of the system. The study chose Thursdays to administer the questionnaires because Thursdays are major lecture days nationwide for NCS, when all correctional officials are generally available regardless of shift schedules (Imobhio, 2023). The sample consisted of 150 (or 75%) male officials and 50 (or 25%) female officials, making a total of 200 participants. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire, and the Pearson Product-Moment correlation coefficient was used for data analysis.

Results

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for vocational training of correctional inmates

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Do Calabar and Obubra corrections have any vocational training/aftercare centre for prison inmates?	200	2.6550	1.01049	-.061	.172	-1.129	.342
Do Calabar and Obubra corrections have earning scheme/one-third remission functional for inmates?	200	2.8150	1.04702	-.472	.172	-.956	.342
Has the concerned authority able to provide vocational tools and other necessary tools that will determine inmates from criminalities on discharge?	200	2.9350	1.05658	-.566	.172	-.938	.342
Have there be any form of settlement for the ex-convict on discharge to start life again?	200	2.5250	1.22756	-.083	.172	-1.587	.342
Valid N (listwise)	200						

The table above shows the responses of respondents to the sub-scale on Vocational Training of Correctional Inmates, with four options: strongly agree, agree, disagree, or strongly disagree. As presented in the table, most respondents either selected strongly agree, agree, disagree, or strongly disagree with the items in this subscale. Presenting results using skewness and kurtosis is important because they indicate the extent to which the variables are not normally distributed. Kline (1998) stated that skewness above 3.0 and kurtosis above 10 indicate serious departures from normality in a distribution. According to these criteria, none of the variables showed issues with normality. However, when examining whether vocational training for correctional inmates leads to crime control in Nigeria, respondents’ observations yielded a mean of 1.01049. To assess if Calabar and Obubra custodial centers have vocational training centers for inmates, the data analysis showed a mean of 2.8150. Additionally, to determine if the correctional authorities or the government provide vocational tools and other resources necessary to help inmates reintegrate after discharge, respondents’ responses indicated a mean of 2.9350. The final item captures respondents’ views on whether there has been some form of settlement for ex-convicts upon discharge to help them start anew, with a mean of 2.5250. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant association between Vocational Training of Correctional Inmates and crime control.

Table 2: Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient analysis for vocational training of correctional inmates and crime control (N=200)

Variables	M	SD	$\sum x$ $\sum y$	$\sum x^2$ $\sum y^2$	$\sum xy$	r-value
vocational training	14.74	1.889	2651	39677		0.190*
crime control	14.09	2.190	2535	36559	37475	

**significant at 0.05 level, df = 198, critical r 0.026

Decision

The Pearson product-moment correlation was used to examine the relationship between vocational training of correctional inmates and crime control. The table above shows that the calculated r-value of 0.190* exceeds the critical r-value of 0.066 at the .05 significance level with 198 degrees of freedom. Based on this, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between vocational training of correctional inmates and crime control was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This indicates that there is a significant relationship between vocational training of correctional inmates and crime control.

Findings

Generally, the study examined correctional inmates' vocational training and crime control in Calabar and Obubra custodial centres. Specifically, the objectives examined the association between vocational training/aftercare services, earning schemes and one-third remission, and crime control. To test the relationship between the above variables, Pearson product-moment correlation was utilized. The result from the findings reveals that the calculated r – value of 0.190* is greater than the critical r -value of 0.066 at .05 level of significance with 198 degrees of freedom.

From this result, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant association between vocational training of correctional inmates and crime control, was rejected, while the alternate hypothesis was accepted. This implies that there is a significant association between vocational training of correctional inmates and crime control. The findings are in agreement with (Ogundipe, 2008; 2010 & 2012) who found that inmates in correctional institutions are effectively trained in the industrial session and are empowered with modern tools for effective rehabilitation to society upon discharged and there is monitoring team that takes care of this; the “welfare service” and the “After-care service officers” of the NCS ensure continuity of trades learnt in the correctional centre. This helps to prevent them from returning to crime. The research paper has therefore chosen correctional vocational training of inmates as the key intervention for crime control. The research also sees vocational training of inmates as a means for the reformation of inmates. It also means changing inmates' values and training them in educational or trade skills to be employable upon discharge.

Conclusion

The study examined correctional inmates' vocational training and crime control in Calabar and Obubra corrections of Cross River State, Nigeria. After details and several analyses were made, the study concluded that there exists a relationship between vocational training of inmates and crime control in Calabar and Obubra correctional institutions. The study further shows that for an effective reformation and crime control to take place, there must be a significant provision of vocational skill training for inmates in the various Nigerian correctional institutions. An improvement on these will significantly enhance good inmates' vocational training in controlling crime and criminality in Nigeria. Resultantly, it was concluded that the effective development in the correctional service can only be attained through consistent and regular vocational training of inmates, improvement in aftercare, an earning scheme, and one-third remission, among others. All these and others would effectively help to control crime and criminality in our modern-day society.

Recommendations

From the findings of this study, the under listed recommendations are made:

- i. Government at all levels should recognize the importance of vocational training of inmates for an effective crime control mechanism. As this would go a long way in restructuring the NCS, which will in turn lead to crime control.
- ii. There should be an effective and efficient vocational inmates training in all Nigerian correctional centres for an effective management process. If this is properly done, it will improve a good correctional service like other corrections in the globe.
- iii. Vocational skill development programmes would help address the increasing cases of recidivism in the study area; these programmes will adequately bring about viable changes. This vital palliative measure would have positive effects on discharged skillful offenders with life-saving supports.
- iv. There should be a total refurbishment of the Aftercare unit, earning scheme, and one-third remission of the correctional institutions for effective and adequate service delivery. This will also control crime and criminality among ex-convicts.

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